

Broadband Connectivity and Scholarly Communication: Enhancing Research Output and Impact

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Abstract: Since the late 1990s, broadband connectivity has significantly increased, transforming education and career opportunities. The Internet enhances access to knowledge and information, leading to better academic outcomes and facilitating research by providing diverse sources. Researchers can now access a wider range of materials online, promoting their research skills.

This chapter investigates how broadband accessibility affects research activity in various countries. Using academic journal articles as a proxy for research activity, the study measures the effects of broadband on publications, citations, and h-index. Findings suggest that broadband access increases the number of journal articles published and citations, with significant policy implications for broadband investment.

Several factors explain how the Internet supports academic publications: free access to journal articles, reduced information costs, new publishing op-

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tions, and efficient communication channels. The Internet also provides user-friendly access through electronic devices, enhancing the distribution and visibility of research.

Overall, the Internet has revolutionized academic content access, enabling global connectivity and fostering innovation in research fields. The proliferation of mobile Internet has further expanded access, making it a crucial tool for creativity and academic growth.

1 Introduction

There has been a significant increase in connection to broadband since the late 1990s. The Internet can assist everybody, at every stage of life, to increase their academic attainments and career opportunities. All facets of our economies and communities are being transformed by the Internet. By increasing the approach to knowledge and information, the Internet can serve people to attain better academic outcomes. One of the most impressive changes the Internet can make is by opening a connection to a larger spectrum of subject matter for learning. Instead of relying primarily on the physical copy of research materials and books, researchers now can have access to diverse sources, and scholars can promote research skills by searching online content on their own.

In this chapter, we investigate how the accessibility of broadband affects research activity in various countries. As a proxy for research activities, we take several academic journal articles published by researchers in the country in a year. In addition to measuring the effects of broadband deployment on academic journal articles, we investigate how broadband affects the citations and h-index, which is an author-level metric that measures both the productivity and citation impact of the publications of a scientist or scholar. The differential effect of broadband on journal articles and citations will have a significant policy implication on deciding how much to invest in broadband expansion. Broadband technology can assist isolated by providing an opportunity to get access to various research spectrum from any corner of the world.

Estimates obtained from Poisson and negative binomial in this study indicate that gaining full access to broadband helps to publish more journal articles. For one more subscription of broadband by a household, the difference in

the logs of expected counts of the number of the journal article is expected to increase by 0.0340 points given the other predictor variables in the model are held constant. This means for every 100 new broadband connection there will be about 3 new journal articles published other things remain the same. Similarly, the results obtained from Poisson regression indicates that for a one-unit increase in broadband availability, the difference in the logs of expected counts of journal articles would be expected to increase 0.00469 units, while holding the other variables in the model constant. In the same manner, for a one-unit increase in broadband access, the difference in the logs of expected counts of the number of citations is expected to increase by 0.0187 units given the other predictor variables in the model are held constant. The results of Poisson regression indicate that for one more broadband availability, the difference in the logs of expected counts of citations would be expected to increase by 0.018 units while holding the other variables in the model constant. Another popular measure to quantify the popularity of research is h-index. The h index is an extensive metric based on analysis of publication data using publications and citations to display a measure of the influence, relevance, and wide impact of an expert's cumulative research contributions. For a one-unit increase in broadband availability, the difference in the logs of expected counts of h-index would be expected to increase by 0.0337 units without controlling other variables. While holding the other variables in the model constant, for every unit increase in broadband availability, the differences in the logs of expected counts of H-index would be expected to increase by 0.0131 units.

There are several reasons why and how the Internet assists researchers and academic publications. First, researchers can get free journal articles with the help of the Internet. The conventional form of academic publications often requires a subscription and is being replaced with free versions.

So traditional paper forms of the journal articles are being increasingly replaced by electronic versions and can be found free on the Internet, which usually consists of working versions placed on the home pages of the authors. Second, the cost of getting information is largely reduced by the Internet. Scientists spend 50-60% of their time interacting, and any innovations that promote their conversation with peers (Björk and Turk, 2000). A significant part of the scientific-communication process consists of presenting investigation results in the form of drafts, seminar reports, and peer-reviewed scholarly papers. On average, scholars read more than 100 such publications per year. This means that they put in weeks every working year looking for and getting pertinent material. There is also a "cost" of opportunities given up because they may overlook significant publications because of not being informed of their presence, or because it is very tiresome or costly to obtain them. Third, the Internet provides an option to publish online, up until a few years ago, the only instrument for publishing academic papers was in the form of journal publication. Since the 1990s, the Internet has transformed the scene dramatically. Presently there are several choices available, for example, electronic-only refereed papers that are available free of charge, authors can keep those papers in their or their institution's home page. Forth, the information transmission channels provided by the Internet makes it much easier for researchers to write fine papers. on the other hand, commercial scientific publishers can get their publication materials via the internet in less time. The tedious process of publication cycle: providing the subject matter, revising, reviewing can be done nowadays with a very small marginal cost. Today the academic scholars set out their articles themselves and the Internet provides an advertising and distribution channel at virtually zero marginal cost. Fifth, online materials are user friendly and can be accessed in any electronic device like a computer,

smartphone, tablet. A study conducted in 1998 by the International Council for Scientific and Technical Information on how researchers use Internet-based services indicated that 61% of respondents felt that electronic publications are user friendly but only 14% of them published the papers (Anon 1999). Thus, it shows that as readers of papers, analysts are highly dynamic and supportive of free electronic publications, but as writers of papers, they are conservative in their decision of where to submit their articles. In an analysis of the economics of electronic publications, Odlyzko (1998) recommends one future scenario: "professors will continue submitting their papers to the most prestigious journals they can find, no matter how small their circulation, since prestige is what counts in tenure and promotion decisions, and since everybody that they want to read their papers will get them electronically from preprint servers in any case."

The Internet has contributed to significant innovations in academic content. Researchers from one corner of the globe can get access to open educational materials and numerous online courses from the other corner with a significantly small amount of time and effort. These can enhance local educational resources, broadening the area and variety of journal articles accessible to scholars. Until recently, the Internet was principally obtained through computers, which were not cheap to most individuals in most communities. However, connection to mobile phones which can be applied to approach the Internet has played a significant part in developing an Internet connection, and as a unique instrument to foster creativity. The magnitude of the research field affects citation counts in several aspects. In extremely limited, self-contained fields, the citation counts can be supposed to be proportional to the number of authors within the field. In extensive research fields, the mean citation numbers may be large. In rapidly developing fields, citation rates will

be large, because the number of citers is big relative to the number of citable materials.

The paper proceeds as follows: The next section briefly reviews the related literature. In Section 3, we discuss the data and descriptive statistics. Section 4 presents the econometric model, section 5 presents results, and Section 6 concludes.

2 Literature Review

One of the primary objectives of research and scientific publications is to increase the frontier of learning. Publications may contribute to the investigator to increase prestige and career advancement. Increasingly investigators are being gauged based upon their publications as well as the number of citations these publications made. One of the key means to strengthen citations is to display the analysis product to a broader public because individuals can only refer to papers that they are familiar of. Internet assists researchers to make their publications more visible as other researchers can get access to papers from any part of the world. Marashi et al. (2013) demonstrate that citations to a paper may strongly depend on visibility. Furthermore, Ebrahim et al. (2013) claim that the promotion and broad dissemination of the publications increase the citations by fifty percent.

The purpose of citations as a quality measure is constructed on the theory that authors make their references on the premise of excellence. Citations are increasingly employed as performance indicators in scientific research. Usually, citations are believed to point out the impact of the research or its quality. Scholars are divided whether citations truly serve as the quality of a journal article. Various authors (Seglen 1997; Coryn 2006; Jarwal et al. 2009; Aksnes et

al. 2019) employed journal article citations as a research quality and scientific impact. Brinn et al.(2000) in a study of UK accounting academics indicates that peer reviews are regarded to be more effective than citation indices.

Fagbule (2018) argues that H-index indicates the academicians' influences in the indicated field of research. Therefore, an individual with higher h-index is more likely to produce high-quality publications with a huge number of citations. Despite its reputation, the index includes several complications. Most notably, it is not field-normalized and no corrections are established for career span, which means that the index disfavors younger researchers (Alonso et al. 2009). The h index is considered having the privilege that it gives a powerful measure of the immense impact of an expert's cumulative research inputs (Hirsch, 2005a). Some authors (Cronin & Meho, 2006; Egghe, 2006b, 2006c) suggests that the h index is passive to a series of lowly cited and non-cited studies or to one or several highly cited journals: An analyst with remarkably few highly cited papers or many lowly cited studies will have a small h index. As a rule, the index supports enduring performers with a constant flow of publications maintaining above-average impact.

Atasoy (2013) in her study on how broadband affects labor market, found that gaining access to broadband services in a county is associated with approximately a 1.8 percentage point increase in the employment rate, with larger effects in rural and isolated areas. Nakyung and Lee(2019) examine the effect of the broadband use on disabled employment in the United States during 2013–2016 using a county-level panel data set and found that, on average, broadband use increases the disabled employment. Yoo et al. (2005) analyze the expansion of the mobile infrastructure in South Korea. Their research indicates that successful innovation and diffusion of broadband mobile services are positively correlated. Muchiri and Karume (2016) established that there

are positive role broadband plays in spurring innovations in Kenya.

3 Data

Our sample consists of a panel of 190 countries around the world between 2000 and 2018 obtained from three different sources. We get data on the number of broadband, telephone, and mobile cellular subscription per hundred people, from the development indicator of the world bank. We employ data on various education statistics like the percentage of people who graduated in different disciplines like science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM), non STEM, research and development expenditure, from the education indicator of the world bank. Our third source is the National Science Foundation (NSF). The National Science Board (NSB) of NSF provides information regarding various aspects of research and development activities by the country for different periods. We extract data about the number of citable documents produced by a country, total citations obtained by that document, and citations per document and H-index from the NSB website(<https://nces.nsf.gov/pubs/nsb20206/technical-appendix>). We match data from those sources to form our sample in this study.

Broadband helps to publish a higher number of journal articles by reducing the time and cost to search for materials online. Research outcome in one corner of the world can be easily accessed by a researcher in another corner of the globe easily. Broadband affects research outcomes in quantitative and qualitative ways. We built up two separate designs to address both aspects. The dependent variable employed to test the quantitative aspect is the number of journal articles published by a country in a given year.

To explore qualitative performance, we utilize a total number of citations

received by a journal article in a year. The underlying logic for this qualitative assessment is that journal articles with a high technological value are more often cited by other journal articles and researchers. Another dependent variable to analyze the qualitative aspect of the research is H-index. The H-index is an indicator that seeks to quantify both the productivity and the impact of a scientist's journal articles. The indicator is based on the collection of the investigator's most cited studies and the number of citations that they have gained in other researcher's journal articles. The H-index was introduced by J.E. Hirsch in 2005 and produced in the Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America. The h index is a quantitative metric based on the investigation of publication data using publications and citations to present "an estimate of the importance, significance, and broad impact of a scientist's cumulative research contributions." According to Hirsch, the h index is described as: "A scientist has index h if h of his or her N_p papers have at least h citations each and the other $(N_p - h)$ papers have $\leq h$ citations each." As an example, an h index of 5 implies that among all publications by one writer, 5 of these publications have obtained at least 5 citations each. Hirsch asserts that the h index is superior to other single-number criteria, such as the overall quantity of studies, the absolute volume of citations, and citations per paper. Several frequently-used databases, such as Elsevier's Scopus, Clarivate Analytics' Web of Science, and Google Scholar provide h index numbers for writers. h - index for a country for a year is calculated by adding h -index for an individual author. In other words, Country's total number of academic journal articles (h) that has received at least h citations is taken as h -index for a country in that year. Total citations at the country level are the sum of citations obtained by all published academic journal articles in a particular year.

Table 1: Summary Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Scientific and technical journal articles	3857	12110.04	58127.88	0	1115765
Citable documents	3477	25838	261750.5	0	1.21e+07
Total citations	3477	492266.5	5737717	0	2.98e+08
citations per document	3477	17.75	13.47	0	199.96
Patent applications(residents)	1986	17711.86	99481.14	1	1476527
Fixed broadband subscriptions	3260	9.27	12.01	0	62.28
Fixed telephone subscriptions	4016	20.14	20.15	0	135.6
Mobile cellular subscriptions	3973	71.8	50.43	0	345.32
Population density	4187	393.6	1815.24	.14	21389.1
Population ages 0-14 (% of total pop.)	3793	29.67	10.69	11.05	50.26
Population ages 15-64 (% of total pop.)	3793	62.7	6.95	47.18	86.4
Population ages 65 and above (% of total pop.)	3793	7.63	5.29	.69	27.58
Percentage of graduates from STEM	949	33.89	10.12	0	75
Percentage of graduates from non STEM	961	63.37	10.94	13.67	91.23
GDP per capita(USD)	1601	14664.56	23270.63	113	189170.9
Gov. exp. on tertiary edu. as % of GDP (%)	1382	.95	.53	0	4
Current exp.on tertiary edu.	1146	89.18	11.14	17.12	100
Government funding per tertiary student, constant PPP	1097	7431.1	7884.36	0	67811.17
Research and development expenditure (% of GDP)	1625	.93	.95	.01	4.58
H-index	3477	225.26	299.58	9	2222

Total citations are the sum of citations received by the academic journal article published in a country within a year by the researchers of that country. citations per document are the ratio of citable documents and total citations obtained by those documents. The percentage of graduates includes the proportion of the population with at least a BS degree. STEM stands for science, engineering, technology, and mathematics. Non STEM includes all other disciplines.

Table 1 displays the summary statistics of each variable we used in our study. We use two specifications: quantitative and qualitative aspects of the research and development. The dependent variable for the quantitative aspect in our model is the number of scientific and technical journal articles (hereafter journal articles) published by a country in a given year. The average number of journal articles published in the world is 12110 while the minimum is 0 and the maximum is 1115765. There are sixty-eight zeros for journal articles. For the qualitative purpose, we take total citations and H-index as a dependent variable. Our primary variable of importance is broadband subscriptions per hundred people. Its mean is 9.27 per hundred and the standard

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

(1)

	articles	broadband	telephone	cellular	popd	pop014	pop1564	pop65nmore	STEM	non STEM	govexpter	R&D exp.
articles	1											
broadband	0.313***	1										
telephone	0.321***	0.512***	1									
cellular	0.0802	0.507***	0.140*	1								
popd	-0.0740	0.0404	0.199**	-0.0255	1							
pop014	-0.176**	-0.477***	-0.619***	-0.408***	-0.0825	1						
pop1564	-0.0403	0.0323	0.224***	0.214***	0.117	-0.717***	1					
pop65nmore	0.283***	0.648***	0.685***	0.394***	0.0173	-0.803***	0.160*	1				
gradstem	0.112	-0.0791	-0.144*	-0.107	-0.166*	0.00605	-0.0444	0.0293	1			
gradnonstem	0.152*	0.179**	0.0261	-0.0539	-0.240***	-0.0619	-0.113	0.184**	0.217***	1		
govexpter	0.293***	0.139*	0.107	0.00172	-0.0840	0.0117	-0.126	0.0907	-0.248***	0.446***	1	
R&D exp.	0.419***	0.662***	0.667***	0.177**	0.0397	-0.390***	-0.0699	0.612***	-0.0680	0.167**	0.274***	1

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

deviation is 12.01. The largest value is 62.28 per hundred people. Research and development expenditure ranges from 0.01 to 4.58 percent of GDP.

Table 2 displays a correlation matrix for our quantitative variable. It demonstrates that the number of journal articles published by a country is positively correlated with broadband access. Similarly, telephone and mobile cellular are also positively associated with journal articles. Population density, number of people age 0 to 14 and population between ages 15 to 64 are negatively correlated with journal articles. All other variables are positively related to the main variable of interest. The correlation matrix, however, is restricted in the information it gives. This is because the pair-wise correlation fails to address simultaneity due to omitted variable bias. Our estimates are based on various regression that addresses the estimation bias due to omitted variables.

Table 3 presents a correlation matrix for our qualitative variable. It demonstrates that the number of citabale documents, total citations are positively correlated with broadband access. Similarly, telephone and mobile cellular are

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

(1)

	citable_documents	citations	citations_per_documents	broadband_100	telePhone per 100	cellular_100	pop1564	pop65nmore	gradstem	gradnonstem	R&D exp.
citable_documents	1										
total citations	0.879***	1									
citations_per_documents	-0.0100	0.211***	1								
broadband_100	0.327***	0.217***	-0.220***	1							
1.2 telePhone per 100	0.285***	0.356***	0.370***	0.553***	1						
cellular_100	0.0760	0.0162	-0.254***	0.490***	0.180**	1					
pop1564	-0.0350	-0.0279	-0.0870	0.0829	0.266***	0.264***	1				
pop65nmore	0.266***	0.277***	0.0430	0.661***	0.704***	0.291***	0.224***	1			
gradstem	0.0837	0.00245	-0.119*	-0.0417	-0.131*	-0.0773	-0.00460	0.00481	1		
gradnonstem	0.197***	0.178**	-0.0333	0.0683	-0.0560	-0.0716	-0.0479	0.137*	0.171**	1	
R&D exp.	0.414***	0.415***	0.225***	0.629***	0.643***	0.171**	-0.0384	0.603***	-0.0407	0.126*	1

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

also positively associated with citations. R&D expenditure, graduates with STEM degree and not STEM degree are also positively correlated with citations.

Figure 1 is the histogram of the number of journal articles published. The figure indicates that the data is not normally distributed; it is highly skewed. This histogram supports our choice for employing count data models. A histogram is made like a bar sketch, but generally takes bars of uneven width. It is the area of the bar that informs us the frequency in a histogram, not its height. Instead of plotting frequency on the y-axis, we plot the frequency density. To determine this, we divide the frequency of a group by the width of it.

Figure 1: Distribution of journal articles

4 Empirical Specification

We Employed two separate models for analysis of our data.

4.1 Poisson and Negative Binomial

The response variable in our model is the number of journal articles published and citations received by published papers. The distribution of counts is discrete, not continuous, and is restricted to non-negative amounts. There are two problems with applying an ordinary linear regression model to these data. First, as we can observe from the histogram, distributions of count data are left-skewed with many observations in the data set that has a value of 0. The large amount of 0's in the data set restricts the transformation of a skewed distribution into a normal one. Second, it is highly possible that the OLS regression model will generate negative predicted values, which are theoretically

inconceivable.

We employ a Poisson regression design and negative binomial. These designs have several advantages over an OLS regression model, consisting of a skew, discrete distribution, and the constraint of estimates to non-negative quantities.

A frequently employed models for the distributions of the count variables Y_{it} are the Poisson regression and Negative binomial model (Greene, 1994; Paul et al., 2002; Johnstone, 2010; Drivas et al., 2015). It assumes that $Y_{i1}, Y_{i2}, \dots, Y_{iT}$ are independent over time conditional on $X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{iT}$, α_i and the conditional distribution of Y_{it} for individual i in time period t , given strictly exogenous regressors X_{it} and an individual effect α_i , is a Poisson distribution with parameter μ_{it} :

$$Pr(Y_{it} = y | \mu_{it}) = Po(y; \mu_{it}) = \frac{\exp(-\mu_{it})(\mu_{it})^y}{y!} \quad (1)$$

for $y = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$, and

$$\mu_{it} = \exp(X_{it}^T \beta + \alpha_i) \quad (2)$$

Here Y_{it} is the number of journal article counts for a country i at time t , X_{it} consists of regressors including the variable of interest: broadband per hundred, control variables are: telephone per hundred, mobile cellular per hundred, number of graduates in-country (it is calculated by adding graduates in all disciplines, in summary, statistics it is presented separately as STEM and non-STEM), research and development funding as a percentage of GDP, government funding per tertiary student and current expenditure in tertiary education. β is a vector of the unknown parameter to be estimated. There is no unanimous view among the researchers about the relationship between

age and productivity of the research. Investigations land into two separate pages, reporting contradictory opinions. One group of researchers (Gieryn 1981; Over 1988; Horner et al. 1986) demonstrate that younger investigators are more productive than older ones while others (Cole 1979; Wray 2004; Kyvik & Olsen 2008) establish that the researchers in the midst of their careers and maturity, rather than the younger ones are the most effective and have a better scientific impact. As we know, that a country with more researchers publishes more journal articles in comparison to a country with a small population. To handle this issue, we have controlled for the population of all age groups: 0-14, 15-64, and more than 65 years. Also, higher investment in research and development leads to higher journal articles, so it is essential to control for R & D. If there are a higher percentage of university graduates, they are more likely to produce the higher number of research outputs; we controlled for graduates which consist of the percentage of university graduates with at least BS degree from various disciplines.

The Poisson model assumes that the data are equi-dispersed: the conditional mean is equal to the conditional variance. To handle the issue of over-dispersion, we use the Negative Binomial (NB), model. The NB model accounts for over-dispersion through an additional parameter $\theta_i \geq 0$ assumed constant over time for a given individual, replacing the distributional assumptions by:

$$Pr(Y_{it} = y | \mu_{it}, \theta_i^{-1}) = \frac{\Gamma(y + \theta_i)}{y! \Gamma(\theta_i)} \left(\frac{\theta_i^{-1}}{\theta_i^{-1} + \mu_{it}} \right)^{\theta_i} \left(\frac{\mu_{it}}{\theta_i^{-1} + \mu_{it}} \right)^y \quad (3)$$

In this paper, we use the parametrization of NB model defined by Hausman

et al.(1981) such that:

$$\mu_{it} = \theta_i \lambda_{it} \quad (4)$$

$$\lambda_{it} = \exp(X_{it}^T \beta) \quad (5)$$

This specification has the advantage that we can estimate using conditional maximum likelihood, in a similar way as the Poisson model with fixed effects: since for a given i , the Y_{it} are assumed to be independent over time. The conditional likelihood distribution of individual i given the total count $\sum_t Y_{it}$ is then given by:

$$L_i = \frac{\Gamma(\sum_t \lambda_{it}) \Gamma(\sum_t Y_{it} + 1)}{\Gamma\left(\sum_t Y_{it} + \sum_t \lambda_{it}\right)} \prod_t \frac{\Gamma(Y_{it} + \lambda_{it})}{\Gamma(Y_{it} + 1) \Gamma(\lambda_{it})} \quad (6)$$

where Y_{it} is dependent variable: number of journal articles published at country-level. X_{it} contains the variable of interest: broadband per hundred. The control variables are same as we used in quantitative model.

5 Results

In this section, we present the results obtained from our baseline models. Table 4 presents the predicted Poisson and negative binomial regression coefficients for the baseline model. Our dependent variable (number of academic journal articles published in a year) is a count variable and Poisson regression models the log of the expected count as a function of the predictor variables.

Column (1) and (2) presents the results obtained from negative binomial regression. For an additional subscription in broadband access, the difference in the logs of expected counts of the number of the journal article is

Table 4: Impact of broadband in number of journal articles

Dependent variable: Journal articles published

Dep.Variable: Journal Articles	(1) NB	(2) NB with controls	(3) Poisson	(4) Poisson with controls
Broadband per 100	0.0340*** (0.000815)	0.00162*** (0.000138)	0.0222*** (1.85e-05)	0.00469*** (0.000162)
Phone per 100		0.00534*** (0.00115)		0.00306*** (0.000167)
Pop. age 0- 14		-0.0115*** (0.0166)		-0.0127*** (0.00163)
Pop. age 64 plus		0.0974*** (0.0115)		0.0482*** (0.00153)
Govt. Exp. Per Tertiary Student		0.00243 (0.00180)		0.00496*** (0.000298)
R& D Exp.		0.0208 (0.0501)		0.0220*** (0.00674)
GDP per capita		0.0176* (0.00899)		0.000251 (0.000958)
Graduates		0.00344 (0.00331)		0.0144*** (0.000505)
Constant	1.629*** (0.0295)	6.103*** (0.592)	8.807*** (0.151)	12.33*** (0.284)
Observations	3,077	128	3,078	132
Number of id	198	22	199	26

Standard errors in parentheses: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

columns 1 and 3 are results without control variables, while columns 2 and 4 present the results obtained by adding control variables. Graduates are the people with at least a BS degree combined with all disciplines. Phone means fixed telephone and mobile cellular.

expected to increase by 0.00162 points given the other predictor variables in the model are held constant. Similarly, the results obtained from Poisson regression indicates that for a one-unit increase in broadband availability(one more broadband connection), the difference in the logs of expected counts of journal articles would be expected to increase 0.00469 units, while holding the other variables in the model constant. We have controlled for the population of all ages: 0-14 and more than 64. The coefficients of the age group 0-14 have a negative coefficient indicating that this age category does not play a role in research activities. In the same way, the population age more than 64 years are comparatively less engaged in research, though it is statistically

significant.

Table 5: Impact of broadband in a number of citable documents

Dependent variable: Citable documents

VARIABLES	(1) NB	(2) NB with controls	(3) Poisson	(4) Poisson with controls
Broadband per 100	0.0253*** (0.00161)	0.00665*** (0.00181)	0.120*** (1.88e-05)	0.00766*** (0.000138)
Phone per 100		0.00638*** (0.00158)		0.00397*** (0.000143)
Pop. Age 0 - 14		-0.0311* (0.0166)		-0.0642*** (0.00142)
Pop. Age 64 plus		0.0926*** (0.0148)		0.0895*** (0.00125)
Gov. Exp. Per Tertiary Student		0.00331 (0.00252)		0.00160*** (0.000258)
R & D Exp		0.232*** (0.0565)		0.154*** (0.00539)
GDP Per capita		0.00866 (0.0107)		0.00265*** (0.000782)
Graduates		-0.00224 (0.00464)		-0.00618*** (0.000425)
Constant	-0.362*** (0.0279)	3.029*** (0.691)	8.179*** (0.141)	9.810*** (0.248)
Observations	2,773	125	2,774	129
Number of id	178	21	179	25

Standard errors in parentheses: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

columns 1 and 3 are results without control variables, while columns 2 and 4 present the results obtained by adding control variables. Graduates are the people with at least a BS degree combined with all disciplines. The number of citable documents published by a journal in the three previous years (selected year documents are excluded). Exclusively articles, reviews, and conference papers are considered.

In table 5, we present the predicted Poisson and negative binomial regression coefficients for the baseline model, where the dependent variable is the number of citable documents. Column (1) and (2) presents the results obtained from negative binomial regression. For a one-unit increase in broadband access, the difference in the logs of expected counts of the number of the citable document is expected to increase by 0.00665 units given the other predictor variables in the model are held constant. Column (3) and (4) tabulates the results of Poisson regression. For a one-unit increase in broadband availability,

the difference in the logs of expected counts of citable documents would be expected to increase by 0.00766 units, while holding the other variables in the model constant.

Table 6, we depict the predicted Poisson and negative binomial regression coefficients for the baseline model, where the dependent variable is the total number of citations in a given year by a country.

Table 6: Impact of broadband in number of total Citations

Dependent variable: Number of citations

VARIABLES	(1) NB	(2) NB with controls	(3) Poisson	(4) Poisson with controls
Broadband per 100	0.00723*** (0.00155)	0.0149*** (0.00568)	0.0669*** (3.24e-06)	0.0108*** (3.05e-05)
Phone per 100		0.00925* (0.00475)		0.0222*** (3.56e-05)
Pop. age 0-14		-0.0408 (0.0336)		-0.0439*** (0.0356)
Pop. age 64 plus		-0.0390 (0.0413)		-0.170*** (0.000307)
Gov. Exp. Per Tertiary Student		0.00276 (0.00887)		0.0213*** (5.95e-05)
R & D Exp.		0.228 (0.143)		0.0172*** (0.00123)
GDP Per capita		0.000592 (0.0447)		0.0597*** (0.000189)
Graduates		0.0293** (0.0124)		0.0324*** (0.000102)
Constant	-0.224*** (0.0280)	1.238 (1.389)	11.71*** (0.147)	10.86*** (0.404)
Observations	2,773	125	2,774	129
Number of id	178	21	179	25

Standard errors in parentheses: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

columns 1 and 3 are results without control variables, while columns 2 and 4 present the results obtained by adding control variables. Graduates are the people with at least a BS degree combined with all disciplines. The number of citations received in the selected year by a journal to the documents published in the three previous years, which means citations received in year n to documents published in years $n-1$, $n-2$, and $n-3$. All types of documents are considered.

Column (1) and (2) presents the results obtained from negative binomial regression. For a one-unit increase in broadband access, the difference in the

logs of expected counts of the number of citations is expected to increase by 0.0149 units given the other predictor variables in the model are held constant. Column (3) and (4) tabulates the results of Poisson regression. For a one-unit increase in broadband availability, the difference in the logs of expected counts of citations would be expected to increase by 0.0108 units, while holding the other variables in the model constant.

Table 7: Impact of broadband in H- index

Dependent variable: H- index

VARIABLES	(1) NB	(2) NB with controls	(3) Poisson	(4) Poisson with controls
Broadband per 100	0.0399*** (0.00152)	0.0131** (0.00544)	0.0337*** (7.71e-05)	0.00870*** (0.000432)
Phone per 100		0.00143 (0.00398)		0.00410*** (0.000374)
Pop. age 0-14		-0.0143 (0.0143)		-0.00494*** (0.00150)
Pop. age 64 plus		0.0343** (0.0175)		0.0623*** (0.00189)
Gov. Exp. Per Tertiary Student		0.00183 (0.00395)		0.00544*** (0.000527)
R & D Exp.		0.608*** (0.0811)		0.407*** (0.00646)
GDP Per Capita		0.0225 (0.0437)		0.0193*** (0.00401)
grad		0.0164 (0.0101)		0.00596*** (0.00107)
Constant	5.062*** (0.0225)	4.667*** (0.761)	5.141*** (0.00170)	4.183*** (0.0876)
Observations	2,774	129	2,774	129 height

Standard errors in parentheses: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Columns 1 and 3 are results without control variables, while columns 2 and 4 present the results obtained by adding control variables. Graduates are the people with at least a BS degree combined with all disciplines. The h index expresses the journal's number of articles (h) that have received at least h citations. It quantifies both journal scientific productivity and scientific impact and it is also applicable to scientists, countries, etc.

In table 7, we take H-index as the dependent variable which is a count variable. Column (1) and (2) presents the results obtained from negative binomial regression. For a one-unit increase in broadband access, the difference in the

logs of expected counts of the H-index is expected to increase by 0.0399 units without controlling for other variables. When the other predictor variables in the model are held constant, for every unit increase in broadband access, the difference in the logs of expected counts of the H-index is expected to increase by 0.0131 units. Column (3) and (4) tabulates the results of Poisson regression. For a one-unit increase in broadband availability, the difference in the logs of expected counts of H-index would be expected to increase by 0.0337 units without controlling other variables. While holding the other variables in the model constant, for every unit increase in broadband availability, the differences in the logs of expected counts of H-index would be expected to increase by 0.0087 units.

Table 8 present the results obtained from Poisson and negative binomial regression based on the income level of countries. To instigate how the relationship between broadband and qualitative and quantitative aspects of research varies in various income level countries around the globe, we employ the classification made by the World Bank.

Table 8: Impact of broadband on number of Journal articles by income level

Dependent Variable: Number of Journal articles VARIABLES	Negative Binomial			Poisson		
	Low income (1)	Middle income (2)	High income (3)	Low income (1)	Middle income (2)	High income (3)
Broadband per 100	0.0186 (0.0272)	0.0171 (0.0144)	0.000913 (0.00215)	0.0259*** (0.000772)	0.0303*** (0.00136)	0.00167*** (0.000159)
Phone per 100	0.0103 (0.0107)	0.0106* (0.00628)	0.00681*** (0.00170)	-0.00296*** (0.000370)	0.00570*** (0.000315)	0.00752*** (0.000174)
Pop. age 0-14	-0.215*** (0.0275)	-0.0746 (0.0626)	-0.00643 (0.0275)	-0.220*** (0.00141)	-0.0541*** (0.00359)	0.0638*** (0.00283)
Pop. age 64 plus	-0.422*** (0.121)	-0.292*** (0.0807)	0.131*** (0.0174)	-0.191*** (0.00290)	-0.00412 (0.00737)	0.108*** (0.00122)
Gov. Exp. Per Tertiary Student	-0.0117 (0.0144)	0.0138 (0.00995)	-0.00127 (0.00344)	0.0369*** (0.000502)	-0.00420*** (0.000437)	0.000749*** (0.000274)
R & D Exp.	1.725* (0.923)	1.817*** (0.396)	0.108 (0.0682)	-0.300*** (0.0164)	0.440*** (0.0268)	0.220*** (0.00618)
Graduates	0.122*** (0.0295)	-0.0299 (0.0354)	0.00616 (0.00489)	0.0818*** (0.000907)	-0.0284*** (0.00118)	0.0124*** (0.000425)
Constant	10.38*** (2.358)	5.096* (2.642)	2.053** (0.906)	8.533*** (0.0855)	10.44*** (0.370)	5.627*** (0.308)
Observations	24	78	108	24	82	109
Number of Countries	10	12	14	10	16	15

Standard errors in parentheses: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Columns 1 and 3 are results without control variables, while columns 2 and 4 present the results obtained by adding control variables. Graduates are the people with at least a BS degree combined with all disciplines. The h index expresses the journal's number of articles (h) that have received at least h citations. It quantifies both journal scientific productivity and scientific impact and it is also applicable to scientists, countries, etc.

We find there is a significant difference in various income level countries. As high-income countries are enjoying the higher speed of the Internet is in the ability to purchase faster internet, they are getting more benefit in terms of publishing more journal articles, keeping the other factors constant. Column (1) of Table 8 presents the results for low-income countries. In both models, we can see the coefficients of broadband are positive but not significant. Also, we get the same magnitude for the broadband coefficient in both Poisson and negative binomial regressions. Column (2) presents the results obtained from negative binomial regression and poisson for middle-income countries. For a one-unit increase in broadband access, the difference in the logs of expected counts of the number of journal articles is expected to increase by 0.0171 units given the other predictor variables in the model are held constant. Column (3) tabulates the results of both models for high-income countries. For a one-unit increase in broadband availability, the difference in the logs of expected counts of journal articles would be expected to increase by 0.000913 units and 0.00167 units respectively for negative binomial and poisson regression, while holding the other variables in the model constant.

Table 9: Impact of broadband on number of citations by income level

Dependent Variable: number of citations	Negative Binomial			Poisson		
	Low income (1)	Middle income (2)	High income (3)	Low income (1)	Middle income (2)	High income (3)
VARIABLES						
VARIABLES	Low income	Middle income	High income	Low income	Middle income	High income
broadband_100	0.00915 (0.0154)	0.00410 (0.0122)	0.0367*** (0.00602)	0.0465*** (0.000239)	0.00510*** (0.000322)	0.0197*** (2.77e-05)
phone_100	0.0139*** (0.00514)	0.00311 (0.00524)	0.0331*** (0.00750)	0.0179*** (0.000231)	0.0105*** (9.16e-05)	0.0346*** (3.25e-05)
pop014	-0.224*** (0.0303)	-0.0334 (0.0480)	-0.0723 (0.0768)	-0.260*** (0.000799)	-0.0531*** (0.000890)	-0.0734*** (0.000506)
pop65nmore	-0.508*** (0.108)	0.0443 (0.0641)	0.0311 (0.0516)	-0.455*** (0.00171)	0.0195*** (0.00180)	0.0786*** (0.000230)
exp_ter	0.0254*** (0.00710)	0.00133 (0.00674)	0.00942 (0.0113)	0.0150*** (0.000195)	0.0137*** (0.000121)	0.00543*** (4.73e-05)
rndexp	2.558*** (0.540)	0.504 (0.346)	0.546*** (0.154)	1.647*** (0.00702)	1.020*** (0.00749)	0.145*** (0.00110)
grad	0.0922*** (0.0144)	0.0226 (0.0264)	0.0650*** (0.0180)	0.0130*** (0.000301)	0.00936*** (0.000355)	0.0640*** (8.19e-05)
Constant	16.15*** (1.742)	1.263 (2.121)	-1.910 (2.474)	21.88*** (0.0478)	10.08*** (0.306)	8.208*** (0.388)
Observations	17	75	108	17	78	109
Number of Countries		11	14		14	15

Standard errors in parentheses: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

columns 1 and 3 are results without control variables, while columns 2 and 4 present the results obtained by adding control variables. Graduates are the people with at least a BS degree combined with all disciplines. The number of citations received in the selected year by a journal to the documents published in the three previous years, which means citations received in year n to documents published in years $n-1$, $n-2$, and $n-3$. All types of documents are considered.

We notice there is considerable variation in different income level states. As high-income countries are experiencing a higher speed of the Internet are capable to acquire faster internet, they are making more benefits in terms of publishing more journal papers and more citations, holding the other factors constant. Another reason for this may be the quality of education in developed countries.

Column (1) of Table 9 displays the results for low-income states. In both designs, we can identify the coefficients of broadband are positive but not significant. Column (2) displays the results attained from negative binomial regression and poisson for middle-income countries. For a one-unit rise in broadband access, the difference in the logs of expected counts of the citations of journal articles is thought to rise by 0.00410 units provided the other predictor variables in the model are held constant. Column (3) tabulates the results of both models for high-income countries. For a one-unit increase in broadband availability, the difference in the logs of expected counts of citations of journal articles would be expected to increase by 0.0367 units and 0.0197 units respectively for negative binomial and poisson regression, while holding the other variables in the model constant.

6 Conclusion

Broadband plays a crucial role in various sectors of the economy. The education sector is not distant from broadband connection. Our sample consists of a group of 190 countries around the globe between 2000 and 2018 obtained from three distinct authorities. We get statistics on the quantity of broadband, telephone, and mobile cellular subscription per hundred individuals, from the development indicator of the World Bank. We utilize data on different edu-

cation statistics like the proportion of individuals who graduated in particular disciplines like science, technology engineering, and mathematics(STEM), research and development expenditure, from the education indicator of the World Bank. Our third source is the National Science Foundation(NSF). The National Science Board(NSB) of NSF provides information concerning different facets of research and development activities by the country for particular times. We obtain informations about the amount of citable documents generated by a country, all citations retrieved by that document, and the H-index from the NSB website. We match data from these three authorities to create our sample in this research.

We employ the count data model as our dependent variable (number of journal articles and citations) is a discrete variable and is non-negative. We compute the quantitative and qualitative facets of broadband on research activities. The excellence of the research paper is captured by applying the number of citations as well as h-index while the quantitative aspect is taken care of by the quantity of journal articles published in the country in a specific time. For the quantitative effect of the broadband, we take the number of journal articles published as a dependent variable, and citations obtained by the paper is taken as the dependent variable for a qualitative side of journal article assuming that a higher quality paper gets more citations.

We find significant effects of broadband on journal articles and citations: For a current subscription in broadband connection, the change in the logs of expected estimates of the number of the journal article is supposed to rise, given the other predictor variables in the design are taken stable. Similarly, the results achieved from Poisson regression suggest that expansion in broadband availability, the variation in the logs of expected counts of journal articles would be predicted to increase while maintaining the other variables in the

design constant. The results of Poisson regression suggest that for one more broadband availability, the difference in the logs of expected counts of citations would be thought to raise while holding the other variables in the model constant. Another popular measure to quantify the popularity of research is the h-index. With more broadband per hundred, the h-index is also tending to increase.

In brief, we can determine that our estimation results present substantial evidence that an increase in the number of broadband connections assist researchers to produce more academic journal papers. The effect is stronger in high-income countries and smaller in low-income countries. This may be related to the quality of broadband, as broadband speed is faster in rich countries and slows in low-income countries. Also, faster internet is more expensive than the slow one and high-income countries may be in a stronger position to seize advantage of high-speed internet.

7 References

- Aksnes, Dag W., Liv Langfeldt, and Paul Wouters. "Citations, citation indicators, and research quality: An overview of basic concepts and theories." *Sage Open* 9, no. 1 (2019): 2158244019829575.
- Ale Ebrahim, Nader, Hadi Salehi, Mohamed Amin Embi, Farid Habibi, Hossein Gholizadeh, Seyed Mohammad Motahar, and Ali Ordi. "Effective strategies for increasing citation frequency." *International Education Studies* 6, no. 11 (2013): 93-99.
- Allison, Paul D., and Richard P. Waterman. "Fixed-effects negative binomial regression models." *Sociological methodology* 32, no. 1 (2002):

- Alonso, Sergio, Francisco Javier Cabrerizo, Enrique Herrera-Viedma, and Francisco Herrera. "h-Index: A review focused in its variants, computation and standardization for different scientific fields." *Journal of informetrics* 3, no. 4 (2009): 273-289.
- BHAVEN, 2011, "USPTO Patent and Citation Data", <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/SJPHLG>, Harvard Dataverse, V4,
- Björk, Bo-Christer, and Ziga Turk. "How scientists retrieve publications: an empirical study of how the Internet is overtaking paper media." (2000).
- Brinn, Tony, Michael John Jones, and Maurice Pendlebury. "Measuring research quality: Peer review 1, citation indices 0." *Omega* 28, no. 2 (2000): 237-239.
- Cronin, B., Meho, L. (2006). Using the h-index to rank influential information scientists. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 57(9), 1275–1278.
- Cole S (1979) Age and Scientific Performance. *Am J Soc* 84: 958–977.
- Coryn, Chris LS. "The use and abuse of citations as indicators of research quality." *Journal of MultiDisciplinary Evaluation* 3, no. 4 (2006): 115-121.
- Drivas, Kyriakos, Irene Fafaliou, Elpiniki Fampiou, and Demetrius Yannelis. "The effect of patent grant on the geographic reach of patent trade." *The Journal of High Technology Management Research* 26, no. 1 (2015): 58-65.

- Egghe, Leo. "How to improve the h-index." *The Scientist* 20, no. 3 (2006): 15-16.
- Egghe, Leo. "An improvement of the h-index: The g-index." ISSI, 2006.
- Fagbule O. F. (2018). USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA TO ENHANCE THE IMPACT OF PUBLISHED PAPERS. *Annals of Ibadan postgraduate medicine*, 16(1), 1-2.
- Greene, William H. "Accounting for excess zeros and sample selection in Poisson and negative binomial regression models." (1994).
- Gieryn TF (1981) The aging of a science and its exploitation of innovation: Lessons from X-ray and radio astronomy. *Scientometrics* 3: 325-334.
- Horner KL, Rushton JP, Vernon PA (1986) Relation between aging and research productivity of academic psychologists. *Psychology and Aging* 1: 319-324.
- Hirsch, J.E. (2005a). An index to quantify an individual's scientific research output. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, USA*, 102(46), 16569-16572
- Jarwal, Som D., Andrew M. Brion, and Maxwell L. King. "Measuring research quality using the journal impact factor, citations and 'Ranked Journals': blunt instruments or inspired metrics?." *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management* 31, no. 4 (2009): 289-300.
- Johnstone, Nick, Ivan Hašič, and David Popp. "Renewable energy policies and technological innovation: evidence based on patent counts." *Environmental and resource economics* 45, no. 1 (2010): 133-155.

- Kyvik S, Olsen TB (2008) Does the aging of tenured academic staff affect the research performance of universities? *Scientometrics* 76: 439–455.
- Marashi, Sayed-Amir, Seyed Mohammad Amin Hosseini-Nami, Khadijeh Alishah, Mahdieh Hadi, Ali Karimi, Saeedeh Hosseinian, Rouhallah Ramezanifard, Reihaneh Sadat Mirhassani, Zhaleh Hosseini, and Zahra Shojaie. "Impact of Wikipedia on citation trends." *EXCLI journal* 12 (2013): 15.
- Odlyzko, Andrew M. "The economics of electronic journals." *Technology and scholarly communication* (1999): 380-393.
- Seglen, Per O. "Citations and journal impact factors: questionable indicators of research quality." *Allergy* 52, no. 11 (1997): 1050-1056.
- Over R (1988) Does scholarly impact decline with age? *Scientometrics* 215–223.
- Wray KB (2004) An examination of the contributions of young scientists in new fields. *Scientometrics* 61: 117–128.

8 Appendix

- World Bank, As of 1 July 2019, classified low-income economies are those with a GNI per capita, of \$1,025 or less in 2018; lower middle-income economies are those with a GNI per capita between \$1,026 and \$3, 995; upper middle-income economies are those between \$3,996 and \$12, 375; high-income economies are those with a GNI per capita of \$12,376 or more. Following are countries in each income level as classified by World Bank.

- High Income countries(including some territories):
 Andorra, Antigua and Barbuda, Argentina, Aruba, Australia, Austria, Bahamas, Bahrain, Barbados, Belgium, Bermuda, British Virgin Islands, Brunei, Canada, Cayman Islands, Chile, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Faroe Islands, Finland, France, French Polynesia, Germany, Gibraltar, Greece, Greenland, Guam, Hong Kong, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Isle of Man, Israel, Italy, Japan, Kuwait, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Monaco, Netherlands, New Caledonia, New Zealand, Northern Mariana Islands, Norway, Oman, Palau, Panama, Poland, Portugal, Puerto Rico, Qatar, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Saint Martin, San Marino, Saudi Arabia, Seychelles, Singapore, Sint Maarten, Slovakia, Slovenia, South Korea, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Taiwan, Trinidad and Tobago, Turks and Caicos Islands, United Arab Emirates, United Kingdom, United States, Uruguay
- Middle Income Countries:
 Angola, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Bolivia, Cambodia, Cameroon, Djibouti, Egypt, El Salvador, Georgia, Ghana, Honduras, India, Indonesia, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Kiribati, Kyrgyzstan, Laos, Lesotho, Mauritania, Micronesia, Moldova, Mongolia, Morocco, Myanmar, Nicaragua, Nigeria, Pakistan, Papua New Guinea, Philippines, Sao Tome and Principe, Solomon Islands, Sri Lanka, Sudan, Tunisia, Ukraine, Uzbekistan, Vanuatu, Vietnam, Zambia
- Low Income Countries: Afghanistan, Benin, Burkina Faso, Central African Republic, Chad, Ethiopia, Gambia, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Haiti, Liberia, Madagascar, Mali, Mozambique, Nepal, Rwanda, Sierra Leone, Tajikistan, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda

- UN classification criteria for countries

As of 1 July 2019, the World Bank classified low-income economies are those with a GNI per capita, of \$1,025 or less in 2018; lower-middle-income economies are those with a GNI per capita between \$1,026 and \$3, 995; upper-middle-income economies are those between \$3,996 and \$12, 375; high-income economies are those with a GNI per capita of \$12,376 or more. This classification of countries based on income level allows us to control for the effect of income on innovation, as people are supposed to be more innovative with higher income.